

THE EFPEKT OF SIDERATE CROPS TO SOIL MOISTURE DYNAMICS IN RAINFED HANDS.

I.Sh.Mamatkulov,

Scientific Research Institute of Rainfed Agriculturt.

e-mail: uzniizerno@yahoo.com

Abstract. *The article presents information on the changes in soil moisture dynamics of siderate crops in the conditions of rainfed gray soils. In November, it was found that in the options planted with siderate crops, compared to the control additional moisture was accumulated. Siderate has a positive effect on the moisture dynamics of crops.*

Key words: *Rainfed areas, gray soils, siderate crops, soil moisture, agrophysical properties of soil, water-physical properties, mechanical composition of soil, water permeability, nutrient regime of soil.*

Introduction. It is important to study the impact of siderate crops on soil fertility and physical properties, which are widespread in arid regions, to improve the agrophysical and agrochemical properties of soils, to effectively use natural moisture, to increase soil fertility and crop yield.

Today, the world's agricultural land area is 1,6 million hectares, of which 1,3 billion hectares are fallow lands, and 60% of agricultural products are grown there. Therefore, the effective use of fallow lands for the cultivation of agricultural products, maintaining and increasing their fertility, and growing various siderate crops to obtain high and quality yields from crops, improving the physical properties of the soil and increasing its fertility are among the important tasks of today.

Analysis of literature on the topic. To meet the growing needs of the population, rational use of land and increased productivity are required. All agrotechnical measures used in the care of agricultural crops primarily affect the soil. As a result, the structure of the soil, its water-physical, physico-chemical properties, its influence on fertility, determine the growth and development of plants, and productivity [11].

When growing the same crop continuously, it is necessary to create the most favorable conditions for the growth and development of the crop in order to obtain the highest yield. If several crops are planted together, it is necessary to create somewhat better conditions for the yield. Because conditions that are unfavorable for one type of crop are favorable for another type of plant, it creates the opportunity to obtain a crop that can compensate for the other [3].

Currently, there are unresolved issues related to maintaining and restoring the fertility of agricultural lands that are difficult to reclaim, particularly gypsum lands, and improving their reclamation status. It is emphasized that the effective use of irrigated gypsum soils in a scientifically and practically based manner is the basis for improving the ecological and reclamation condition of agricultural lands, preserving, restoring and increasing soil fertility, and protecting it. It is emphasized that the effective use of gypsum soils will ensure the food security of our country and further increase the well-being of our people. [7].

The agrophysical properties of the soil depend primarily on the mechanical composition of the soil. Most agrophysical properties of soils with a heavy mechanical composition are superior to those of soils with a light mechanical composition. However, in heavy soils, indicators such as density, porosity, and water permeability are in poor condition. Light soils often have low field moisture capacity and water-holding capacity. Increasing the humus content in the soil has been shown to improve the agrophysical properties of both heavy and light mechanical soils [8].

From the results of the research by I.A. Tursunov and D. Nurmatova, it can be concluded that when intercrops (rapeseed + vetch) were mixed in the fields cleared from winter wheat in a 1:1 crop rotation system, 58.6 s/ha of stubble and root residues remained in the soil, as a result of which the bulk density of the soil decreased by 0.04-0.03 g/cm³ and its water permeability was high [4].

According to the studies of N.T. Khalmanov, M.A. Elmurodova, the decrease in bulk mass when using siderates occurs most in the upper plowed layer, which creates good conditions for microorganisms. The use of siderates improves the dynamics of the content of humus, total nitrogen and phosphorus, nitrate nitrogen and available phosphorus in all studied soil types and subtypes. This helps to improve the nutrient regime of the soil. Siderates significantly increase the number of microorganisms belonging to taxonomic groups - bacteria, fungi and molds - by improving the water, air and nutrient regimes of the soil [10].

Research methodology. Field experiments in the research were carried out based on the "Methodical Guide to Conducting Field Experiments" [1] developed by scientists of UzPITI, soil analyses were carried out based on the "Manual on Chemical Analysis of Soils" by Y.V. Arinushkina, statistical analyses of the results were carried out based on the "Methodology of Field Experiments" methodical guides by B.A. Dospekhov, and all agro-technological measures were carried out based on the agro-recommendations developed by the Rainfed Agricultural Research Institute. [2].

Field-experimental research on the impact of siderate crops on soil fertility and physical properties in Lalmikor fields was conducted at the Central Experimental Farm of the Lalmikor Agricultural Research Institute of Gallaorol district.

The field experimental sites of the Lalmikor Agricultural Research Institute are located in the semi-arid mountainous region of Lalmikor lands, at an altitude of 580 meters above sea level. The average annual precipitation is 362 mm, varying from 141,2 mm to 616,7 mm over the years. Precipitation falls mainly in the winter and spring months. The average annual temperature is 11,6 °C, with the highest temperature reaching 45 °C in July. Hot days last 170-250 days a year. The lowest temperature is -37 °C in January. The average relative humidity in July is 23-30%. The average number of frost-free days is 171 days. The last spring frost falls on the first ten days of April, while the first, autumn frost begins in the third ten days of September and the first ten days of October.

In the agricultural year of the experiment, the amount of precipitation was 363,7 mm, the annual average air temperature was 10,2 °C, and the relative humidity was 67,0%. These indicators indicate that during the study years, the air temperature was -2,4 °C, the relative humidity was -3,0%, and the amount of precipitation was +1,8 mm higher than the multi-year norm. As a result, the amount of precipitation in March and April was half the average multi-year norm, which negatively affected the level of biomass accumulation of siderate crops.

The total area of the experiment is 0,16 hectares. 3 options. 1 plot size (3 m x 60 m) = 180 m². The natural moisture content of soil samples was determined before planting siderat crops and during the main development periods.

Analysis and results. The dynamics of soil moisture changes in the Lalmikor fields before the experiment in February was determined to be 155,7-177,6 m³/ha in the 0-10 and 10-20 cm layers of the control perennial wheat field, 159,4-164,0 m³/ha in the Triticale + chickpea variant, and 143,9-160,3 m³/ha in the Barley + chickpea variant, respectively.

During the April vegetation period, it was noted that in variant 1, the soil layers 0-10 and 10-20 cm were 113,7-127,0 m³/ha, in variant 2, the soil layers 0-10 and 10-20 cm were 141,7-147,3 m³/ha, and in variant 3, the soil layers 0-10 and 10-20 cm were 133,0-129,4 m³/ha.

Figure 1. The process of determining the amount of moisture in the soil.

During the May vegetation period, the soil moisture content in the 0-10 and 10-20 cm layers of the soil in option 1 was 68,9-73.1 m³/ha, in option 2 it was 72,0-76,8 m³/ha in the 0-10 and 10-20 cm layers, and in option 3 it was 81,1-81,4 m³/ha in the 0-10 and 10-20 sm layers.

The experimental variants were plowed to a depth of 20-22 sm in the first ten days of May. The experimental variants determined the amount of soil moisture in November in the 0-100 cm layer of soil. The results obtained were as follows.

In the control (chronic wheat) sown variant, it was found that the soil in the 0-10 cm layer of soil was 3,09 % or 36.77 m³/ha, and in the 10-20 sm layer it was 3,95% or 47,79 m³/ha, in the 2nd variant, it was 3,48 or 41,4 m³/ha, in the 10-20 sm layer it was 4,51% or 71.38 m³/ha, in the 3rd variant, it was 3,33 or 39.62 m³/ha, and in the 10-20 sm layer it was 3,65% or 44,2 m³/ha.

Conclusions and suggestions. The above results show that in the options with siderat crops planted, we can see that in November, 40,4-69,3 m³/ha of additional moisture accumulated in the 0-100 cm layer of the soil compared to the area planted with Control (Perennial wheat). This has a positive effect on the timely germination and development of winter cereal crops in the fallow areas.

REFERENCES

1. Methods of conducting field experiments // UzPITI, Tashkent, 2007, -B. 1-146
2. Dospekhov B.A. Methodology of polevogo opyta (с основами statisticheskoy obrabotki обработки исследований) Moscow. Agropromizdat, 1985. -351 p
3. Karimova M.A. "The importance of intercropping of grain and leguminous forage crops in the national economy" 1st Republican scientific online conference on "Science problems in the interpretation of young researchers". 2022. 176-178 p.
4. Kurdashev Q.D. "The impact of the gypsum process on soil fertility" Science and innovation international scientific journal. Volume 1 ISSUE 5 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337. 198-202 p.
5. Muratkasimov A.S., Usmonov U.Z. Agro physical features of gray soils in dry land that are exposed to erosion //Texas Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences. – 2023. – T. 18. – P. 30-31.
6. Nishanov J.A., Yusupov H., Muratkasimov A.S. The effect of tillage technologies in arable fields on the emergence of winter wheat and the number of weeds //Prospects of development of science and education. – 2023. – T. 19. – No. 23. – P. 303-305.
7. Ortikov T.Q., Boyturaev N., Eshmanov B. "The influence of soil mechanical structure and humus state on its water properties" Samarkand branch of Volume 3 | SB TSAU Conference | 2022 Tashkent State Agrarian University Theoretical and Practical Principles of Innovative Google Scholar indexed Development of the Agricultural

Sector in Uzbekistan. October 5-6 www.samaguni.uz Republican Scientific and Practical Conference 2022. 711-715 p.

8. Tursunov I.A., D. Nurmatova “The effect of planting vetch and rapeseed after winter wheat on the agrophysical properties of the soil” *Life Sciences and Agriculture 2.1* – 2020. p. 126-130.

9. Khaidarov B.D., Muratkasimov A.S., Khalikulov D.Kh. Cravnitelnaya effektivnost razlichnyx scheme zernoparopashnyx sevooborotov na bogarnyx zemlyakh respubliky Uzbekistan //BBK 40 A 265 Nauchnaya redkollegiya: YuN Zubarev, dr. s.-x. nauk, professor; SL Eliseev, dr. nauk, professor; ED Akmanaev, candidate s.-x. nauk, professor; AS Bogatyreva, cand. s.-x. nauk, do. - 2015. - S. 140.

10. Khalmanov N.T., Elmurodova M.A. “The influence of siderosis on the fertility of gray soils, growth, development and yield of cotton in the Zerafshan Valley” *Plodorodie* 2019 y. №2. p. 34-36.

11. Khoshimov I.N., Khudoyberdiyeva Sh.D., “The importance of companion crops in repeated cropping” “Interpretation and Research” scientific and methodological journal №13 2022 yil. p. 31-33